

Theory and Sensitivity Optimization of Plasmo-photonic Mach-Zehnder Interferometric Sensors

E. Chatzianagnostou, A. Manolis, A. Miliou, D. Tsiokos, and N. Pleros

Abstract—We demonstrate a novel theoretical framework for refractive index Mach-Zehnder interferometric (MZI) sensors that can accurately calculate the sensor FSR and sensitivity while taking into account waveguide effective index dispersion and dip splitting effects. In contrast to the state-of-the-art mathematical equation that relates sensitivity with FSR, our analysis concludes to a mathematical expression that retains its validity and accuracy both in low and large FSR sensor layouts, suggesting its suitability for use in optimizing sensor performance even in the high-sensitivity, high-FSR configurations. This is validated by applying our theory to integrated plasmo-photonic MZI sensors with FSR values up to hundreds of nm, confirming our theoretical results through accurate numerical and circuit-level simulations and demonstrating how sensitivity can be boosted to $>10^5$ nm/RIU values exploiting dispersion engineering of the waveguides. To this end, our analytical formula that relates sensitivity with FSR and waveguide effective index dispersion can lead to reliable designs and well-matched fabricated modules when targeting high FSRs and high sensitivity MZI photonic integrated sensors.

Index Terms—Dispersion engineer, free spectral range, interferometric sensors, photonic integrated circuits, plasmonics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Photonic sensors based on integrated optics (IO) have attracted intense research interest for the detection of chemical and biomedical analytes since they offer the advantage of high sensitivity, real-time and label-free operation in combination with multiplexed capabilities and in some cases the potential to realize mass produced disposable cartridges at a low cost. The detection principle of integrated photonic sensors is based on the evanescent wave mechanism [1], [2], with their sensitivity being determined by two factors: i) the transducer waveguide sensitivity, S_{WG} , that depends on the effective refractive index sensitivity of the waveguide to the test analyte, and ii) the device sensitivity, which depends on the overall photonic circuit architecture. Waveguide sensitivity represents the effective index change of the waveguide mode

upon a change in the refractive index of the surrounding environment and increases for waveguides that support an enhanced evanescent field, like TM-operated photonic [3], slot-based [4], [5], sub-wavelength grating (SWG) [6], porous silicon [7], and plasmonic waveguides [8]. On the other hand, device sensitivity is determined by the overall photonic circuit architecture that is responsible for transforming the inherent transducer waveguide sensitivity into an interpretable and, most often, magnified device sensitivity. Sensitivity enhancement is an important part of the sensor design process when aiming at the detection of small variations of the parameter under test (e.g. concentration of biomolecules). This becomes even more essential when regular low-cost measurement instruments (e.g., low resolution OSA) are used. Several types of structures have been investigated so far for the implementation of photonic integrated sensors, including strip or slot waveguides incorporated either in resonant structures like ring resonators (RRs) [3], [6], [7], [9], [10] and photonic crystal cavities (PhCs) [11], [12], or in interferometric layouts like Mach-Zehnder [13]–[15] and Young configurations [16], [17].

Resonant structures can yield ultra-compact structures, but their bulk sensitivity has been limited to values around 500-700 nm/RIU for RRs [6], [10] and 1500 nm/RIU for PhCs [12] even when waveguides and configurations with enhanced waveguide sensitivity are utilized. Significant sensitivity enhancement can be achieved by expanding the circuit architecture to exploit, for example, the Vernier effect with two [18], [19] or three cascaded ring resonators [20], leading to bulk sensitivities up to 24300 nm/RIU [19], however at the expense of circuit simplicity and system stability. On the other hand, MZIs are more tolerant and versatile structures that can be designed to provide higher sensitivity values. The most common technique to boost device and, thus, overall sensitivity is to increase the sensing waveguide length in the order of several millimeters or even centimeters, which comes at the expense of compactness [15], [21]–[23] and operational robustness. In addition, sensitivity can be improved by incorporating waveguides that

“This work was supported in part by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme projects Plasmofab (688166) and GRACED (101007448), and the European Regional Development Fund and Research and Innovation Foundation of Cyprus projects (LOTTO (CONCEPT/0618/0038) and MultiCare (SEED/0719/0127)).”

E. C., A. M. and N. P. Authors are with Department of Informatics, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 10th km Thessalonikis-Thermis Av., 57001, Greece (e-mail: evachat@csd.auth.gr, amiliou@csd.auth.gr, npleros@csd.auth.gr).

A.M. Author is with Department of Informatics, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 10th km

Thessalonikis-Thermis Av., 57001, Greece, and bialoom Ltd, 72, 28th Octovriou Avenue, Office 301, Engomi, 2414 Nicosia, Cyprus (e-mail: athanasm@csd.auth.gr).

D. T. Author was with Department of Informatics, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 10th km Thessalonikis-Thermis Av., 57001, Greece, and bialoom Ltd, 72, 28th Octovriou Avenue, Office 301, Engomi, 2414 Nicosia, Cyprus. Now he is only with bialoom (e-mail: info@bialoom.com).

exhibit high field confinement in the low index material like horizontal or vertical slot-based waveguides, but even in this case the sensing lengths are required to extend into the centimeter scale in order to allow for high sensitivity values up to 17000 nm/RIU [4], [14]. Apart from retaining system compactness, the sensing waveguide length needs to be minimized in order to maintain system stability, and operational robustness in practical applications.

To this end, scaling the sensitivity to ultra-high values while retaining a short transducer length has to proceed along the optimal selection of both the waveguide structure and the circuit architecture, building upon the best-in-class waveguide and device sensitivity values, respectively. Within this frame, plasmonics can offer significant benefits compared to photonic waveguides when employed as the transducer element, taking advantage of their increased mode exposure to the overlying analyte towards higher waveguide sensitivity values. The inherent loss-related drawbacks of all-plasmonic structures can be partially counterbalanced by the selective integration of plasmonic waveguides in the sensing arm of low-loss photonic interferometric structures. This scheme leverages the enhanced waveguide sensitivity of plasmonic waveguides with the low-loss passive circuitry portfolio of photonics to realize ultra-sensitive sensors in smaller footprints. Following this approach, a few sensing devices have been experimentally demonstrated so far by using plasmonic transducer elements into a range of photonic circuit architectures [10], [24]–[26]. In this context, the authors have recently demonstrated how a CMOS-compatible plasmo-photonic MZI sensor can lead to bulk sensitivities close to 5000 nm/RIU [27]. The authors have also reported how sensitivity can be boosted to values greater than 60000 nm/RIU by increasing the sensor free spectral range (FSR) and without altering the transducer length [28].

Despite the clear evidence for the potential benefits of such sensing structures, a deeper yet simple theoretical model capturing the underlying physical mechanisms involved when increasing the FSR, deemed necessary for pushing further the sensor sensitivity and for ensuring design reliability in the device fabrication stage. The current approach for calculating the sensitivity of a MZI sensor of known (experimentally measured) FSR relies on the assumption of zero dispersion concluding to an almost linear relationship between sensitivity and FSR [28]. Although this approach is valid for rather low FSR values, it deviates significantly as the FSR increases, which is indeed the case when an MZI device with high sensitivity is the target [28]. The pronounced effect of dispersion engineering has been already outlined both in integrated photonic MZIs [29]–[33] and microfiber-based MZIs [34]–[36], without concluding, however, to a univocal mathematical expression that relates sensitivity with both the sensor FSR and the waveguide dispersion characteristics. To this end, a theoretical tool to reliably explore high-FSR interferometers and accurately design ultra-sensitive integrated MZI sensors of this regime, is clearly missing.

In this paper, we present for the first time a solid theoretical framework that can accurately calculate both the sensor FSR and its sensitivity, concluding to a mathematical expression that

relates the sensor sensitivity with its FSR while taking into account both the dispersion and the dip splitting effects [32]. In contrast to the state-of-the-art mathematical relationship between sensitivity and FSR, our theory retains its validity and accuracy for both the sensitivity and FSR parameters for any FSR value, including the regime of high-FSR designs that yield higher sensitivities [28]. We validate our theory through numerical and circuit-level simulations implemented for plasmo-photonic MZI sensors with FSR values up to hundreds of nanometers, confirming its suitability for optimizing sensor performance and demonstrating how sensitivity can be boosted to $>10^5$ nm/RIU by simply optimizing the width of the photonic or plasmonic waveguides. We believe that our analytical formula that relates sensitivity with FSR of MZI-based sensors, either photonic or plasmo-photonic, can allow for reliable design and sensitivity optimization of high-FSR sensors during the design phase while ensuring better match between predicted and measured sensitivity before and after the device fabrication.

II. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Fig. 1(a) depicts a top-view of the integrated MZI-based refractive index sensor that has been used for our theoretical analysis and for the validation of our theory via numerical simulations. It is a simplified version of the configuration reported in our previous work [28]. The photonic waveguide platform is based on a 360 nm thick Si_3N_4 core lying on top of a 2.2 μm thick SiO_2 substrate layer and cladded with a layer of low-temperature oxide (LTO). A 70 μm long, water-cladded gold stripe is incorporated in the upper Si_3N_4 arm serving as the sensing transducer. In the reference arm, a phase shifter (PS) element and an attenuator (A) are used in order to tune the spectral dip of the interferometer at the desired wavelength and

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic of the plasmo-photonic sensor under investigation, (b) cross-section of the Si_3N_4 photonic waveguide along with the supported TM mode and (c) cross-section of the Au-based plasmonic stripe waveguide along with the supported SPP mode.

to balance the optical losses between the two arms, respectively. The cross-sections of the two waveguides (photonic and plasmonic) along with the supported TM modes are shown in Fig. 1(b) and 1(c), respectively.

The spectral response of a MZI structure varies sinusoidally with wavelength and depends on the phase difference $\Delta\phi$ between the propagating beams along the two arms according to equation 1, where I_0 represents the signal intensity at the MZI output, L_1 and L_2 the lengths of the two interferometric arms and β_1, β_2 the respective propagation constants [37].

$$I_o = \cos^2\left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{2}\right), \quad \Delta\phi = \beta_1 L_1 - \beta_2 L_2 \quad (1)$$

Consequently, the MZI sensor output exhibits transmission peaks and dips that correspond to constructive and destructive interference of light propagating along the reference (arm 1, denoted in this analysis by 'r') and sensing arm (arm 2, denoted by 's').

The wavelengths where a dip occurs are given by equation (2) and are determined by the propagation constants β_r and β_s of the *reference* and *sensing* arm, respectively, with $\beta = 2\pi n_{\text{eff}} / \lambda$, $n_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ph}}$ being the effective index of the photonic waveguides, L_{ph}^r and L_{ph}^s being the photonic waveguide lengths at the reference and sensing arm, respectively, $n_{\text{eff}}^{\text{pl}}$ the effective index of the plasmonic waveguide employed in the sensing arm with L_{pl} its corresponding waveguide length and k being the half integer that represents the interference order.

$$\lambda_{\text{dip}}^k = \frac{n_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ph}} L_{\text{ph}}^r - (n_{\text{eff}}^{\text{pl}} L_{\text{pl}} + n_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ph}} L_{\text{ph}}^s)}{k} \quad (2)$$

In principle, the sensitivity of an optical sensor operating with spectral interrogation is defined by the amount of wavelength shift caused by the effective index change of the mode propagating along the sensing waveguide due to a change in the ambient refractive index. This change can be caused in different ways, such as compositional changes of the cladding/surrounding medium or temperature. For the plasmo-photonic sensor under investigation, this wavelength shift is in principle caused by the change of the effective index of the plasmonic mode, which is highly sensitive to environmental changes due to the profound exposure of the plasmonic mode to the medium residing on top of the metallic stripe. However, taking into account waveguide dispersion, the induced wavelength shift ($\Delta\lambda_{\text{dip}}$) will subsequently influence the n_{eff} of the waveguides in both arms at the new spectral dip. Considering a first order approximation of dispersion, these effects can be decoupled [38]. Moreover, assuming that the photonic waveguide sections are covered with a cladding material that isolates the photonic modes from the surrounding environment, it is obvious that the photonic mode is only affected by dispersion while the plasmonic mode is affected by both phenomena. Consequently, sensitivity is given by the following equation stemming from (2)

$$S = \Delta\lambda_{\text{dip}}^k = \frac{\Delta n_{\text{eff}}^{\text{pl}} \big|_{\text{disp}} L_{\text{pl}}^r - (\Delta n_{\text{eff}}^{\text{pl}} \big|_{\text{env}} + \Delta n_{\text{eff}}^{\text{pl}} \big|_{\text{disp}}) L_{\text{pl}} - \Delta n_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ph}} \big|_{\text{disp}} L_{\text{ph}}^s}{k} \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta n_{\text{eff}} \big|_{\text{env}} = (\partial n_{\text{eff}} / \partial n_{\text{env}}) \Delta n_{\text{env}}$ represents the effective index change due to the refractive index change of the medium surrounding the plasmonic waveguide (Δn_{env}), which is equal to the S_{WG} , and $\Delta n_{\text{eff}} \big|_{\text{disp}} = (\partial n_{\text{eff}} / \partial \lambda)_{\lambda_{\text{dip}}} \Delta \lambda_{\text{dip}}$ represents the effective index change due to dispersion. Numerical simulations have shown that $\Delta n_{\text{eff}} \big|_{\text{env}} \approx 1$ for the specific plasmonic stripe waveguide which means that a unary change of the refractive index of the liquid under test results in a unary change of the plasmonic effective index [39]. Substituting the above result as well as k from (2) into (3), and introducing the group index as $n_g = n_{\text{eff}} - \lambda (dn_{\text{eff}} / d\lambda)$, sensitivity can be expressed through the following compact formula

$$S = \Delta\lambda_{\text{dip}}^k = \frac{L_{\text{pl}} \lambda_{\text{dip}}^k}{\Delta(n_g L)} \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta(n_g L) = n_g^{\text{ph}} L_{\text{ph}}^r - n_g^{\text{pl}} L_{\text{pl}} - n_g^{\text{ph}} L_{\text{ph}}^s$.

Adoption of the well-known equation that gives the FSR of a MZI [37] into (4) leads to the following equation

$$S = \frac{L_{\text{pl}} \text{FSR}_{\text{loc}}}{\lambda_{\text{dip}}} \quad (5)$$

with

$$\text{FSR}_{\text{loc}} = \frac{\lambda_{\text{dip}}^2}{\Delta(n_g L)} \quad (6)$$

being derived from the 1st order approximation of the phase difference, $\Delta\phi$, between the two arms with respect to wavelength. This means that the FSR of the sensor is calculated by assuming $\Delta\phi$ to be a linear function of wavelength with a slope equal to the 1st order derivative of $\Delta\phi$ at the wavelength dip of interest. However, this can't be the case in a dispersive medium where $\Delta\phi$ is by no means a linear function of wavelength and the above approximation can be considered as accurate only around the wavelength dip. To this end, this FSR is only an approximated FSR value that is obtained through the localized $\Delta\phi$ behavior around the wavelength dip and will be called hereafter as '*local*' FSR, defined by the symbol FSR_{loc} . This parameter can approximate the '*real*' FSR of the device, i.e. the FSR that could be experimentally measured after fabrication of the device, when this has a rather small value, since in that case the two adjacent wavelength dips extend along a rather narrow spectral regime where indeed the waveguide dispersion can be considered linear. In such regime, the 1st order dependence of $\Delta\phi$ on wavelength can closely resemble the reality. However, in the case of large FSR values, the neighboring dip moves away from the linear dynamic range so that the 1st order approximation of $\Delta\phi$ cannot capture the dispersion effect and is not any more valid, leading to significant deviations between the '*local*' and the '*real*' FSR values.

The increasing deviation between '*local*' and '*real*' FSR values as well as between the linear and real dependence of $\Delta\phi$ on wavelength as the FSR increases is shown graphically in Fig.

2, where phase difference ($\Delta\phi$) between the two arms of the plasmophotonic MZI sensor under investigation versus wavelength is depicted for configurations with different FSR values. The curves have been obtained by means of broadband circuit-level numerical simulations taking into account material and waveguide dispersion according to the procedure described in [28] for an MZI sensor employing an 800 nm wide Si_3N_4 photonic waveguide and a 7 μm wide plasmonic stripe. Since all phenomena were taken into account during those simulations, we consider the obtained FSR values as ‘real’. The tangent of each $\Delta\phi$ curve at the spectral dip of interest has been also plotted in order to illustrate the case of the linear dependence of $\Delta\phi$ that defines the ‘local’ FSR. As shown in the graph, the tangent of the $\Delta\phi$ can follow very closely the real $\Delta\phi$ curve within a limited spectral region of around 50 nm to the left of the wavelength dip, suggesting that the ‘local’ FSR value has a rather small deviation from the real FSR value when FSRs up to 50 nm are employed. However, when the FSR exceeds 50 nm this deviation starts to get gradually increased with increasing FSR, as can be highlighted in the two cases of 150 nm and 250 nm real FSR values depicted in the graph where the respective ‘local’ FSR values equal 215 nm and 625 nm, respectively. This discrepancy between the ‘local’ FSRs given by (6) and ‘real’ FSR values suggest that employing the real FSR of a device into (5) will yield a significantly different sensitivity value compared to the potential experimental value after fabrication. This signifies that (5) and (6) are not suitable for efficiently correlating the device sensitivity with its real FSR value when high-sensitivity MZI sensors with FSRs exceeding 50 nm are targeted. In order to calculate accurately the expected sensitivity of a sensor with a certain, high real FSR, a new set of equations is needed: firstly, a reliable formula that will be able to predict the real FSR of a certain sensor device, and then, an equation that will relate the sensor sensitivity with its real FSR.

In order to conclude to a more accurate formula for the calculation of FSR, higher order terms are required in the

Fig. 2. $\Delta\phi$ between the two arms for different FSR values versus wavelength for the plasmophotonic MZI sensor under investigation, (dashed lines): tangent of $\Delta\phi$ curve at the spectral dip of interest showing the difference between ‘real’ and ‘local’ FSR. Each point marked with a cross corresponds to odd multiples of π , representing a wavelength dip. FSR corresponds to the spectral difference between two consecutive dips with a $\Delta\phi$ difference of 2π .

approximation of $\Delta\phi$. Thus, we express $\Delta\phi$ as a parabola by means of a 2nd order Taylor series expansion around λ_{dip} that can be easily transformed into the following quadratic equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \Delta\phi}{\partial \lambda^2} FSR^2 + \frac{\partial \Delta\phi}{\partial \lambda} FSR + \Delta\phi|_{FSR} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } \frac{\partial \Delta\phi}{\partial \lambda} = -\frac{2\pi}{\lambda^2} \Delta(n_g L) \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Delta\phi}{\partial \lambda^2} = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda^3} \left[\Delta(n_g L) + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} \Delta\left(\frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right) \right] \text{ with}$$

$$\Delta\left(\frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right) = \frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} \Big|_{ph}^r L_{ph}^r - \frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} \Big|_{pl} L_{pl} - \frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} \Big|_{ph}^s L_{ph}^s.$$

This approximation can be valid as long as $\Delta\phi$ is either a monotonically increasing or decreasing function within a certain wavelength range, or exhibits a local extremum. For the first two cases, $FSR = \lambda_{dip}^k - \lambda_{dip}^{k+1}$ corresponds to a phase difference $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = \Delta\phi_{\lambda_k} - \Delta\phi_{\lambda_{k+1}}$ of $\pm 2\pi$ between the two resonant wavelengths, depending on the monotonicity of the function. When a local extremum exists, $\Delta\phi|_{FSR}$ can be equal to zero, potentially resulting to the dip splitting effect which refers to the phenomenon of splitting or bifurcation of the wavelength dip during a sensing measurement and has been previously reported in [32].

Solving (7) for the three possible values of $\Delta\phi|_{FSR}$ concludes to the FSR solutions determined by 8(a), 8(b) and 8(c), respectively, revealing that FSR depends not only on $\Delta(n_g L)$ like in the case described by (6), but also on the 2nd order dispersion properties of the waveguides declared by the 2nd order derivative of n_{eff} through $\Delta\left(\frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right)$.

More specifically, when $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = \pm 2\pi$:

$$FSR = \frac{-\frac{\partial \Delta\phi}{\partial \lambda} \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \Delta\phi}{\partial \lambda}\right)^2 \mp 4\pi \frac{\partial^2 \Delta\phi}{\partial \lambda^2}}}{-\frac{\partial^2 \Delta\phi}{\partial \lambda^2}} \Rightarrow$$

$$FSR_{2\pi} = -\frac{\lambda}{2} \frac{\Delta(n_g L) + \sqrt{\Delta(n_g L)^2 - 4\lambda \Delta(n_g L) - 2\lambda^3 \Delta\left(\frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right)}}{\Delta(n_g L) + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} \Delta\left(\frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right)}$$

(8a)
and

$$FSR_{-2\pi} = -\frac{\lambda}{2} \frac{\Delta(n_g L) - \sqrt{\Delta(n_g L)^2 + 4\lambda \Delta(n_g L) + 2\lambda^3 \Delta\left(\frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right)}}{\Delta(n_g L) + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} \Delta\left(\frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right)}$$

(8b)

while in the case of $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = 0$,

$$FSR_0 = -\lambda \frac{\Delta(n_g L)}{\Delta(n_g L) + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} \Delta\left(\frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right)} \quad (8c)$$

In order to verify the validity of the new equations, we plotted the theoretically obtained FSR values from (6) and (8) versus the length of the reference photonic waveguide for a sensor with 360×800 nm photonic waveguides and $7 \mu\text{m} \times 100$ nm plasmonic waveguide in Fig. 3, together with the FSR value provided through circuit-level simulations conducted in Lumerical Interconnect platform [40] employing 2D numerical simulations for modelling the waveguide modes by means of Lumerical Mode Solutions [41], as described in [28]. The sensor was configured to exhibit a wavelength dip at 1525 nm and the dispersion characteristics (n_g , $\partial^2 n_{eff} / \partial \lambda^2$) required in the equations were calculated at the same wavelength. It should be noted that FSR values calculated through the circuit-level simulations could not be obtained for certain reference waveguide lengths (specifically in the region between 586-588 μm with regard to Fig. 3), since in these cases the second dip turned to be outside the simulated wavelength range of 1200-1600 nm. As such, only sensor configurations with FSR values up to 325 nm could be evaluated via circuit simulations.

The blue curve in Fig. 3, which illustrates the results from (8a), (8b) and (8c), consists of three parts from left to right corresponding to the three versions of the equation: for $L \leq 586$ μm the results correspond to $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = +2\pi$ or a monotonically increasing function described by (8a), for $586 < L \leq 591.4$ μm correspond to $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = 0$ or a function with a local extremum described by (8c) and for $L > 591.4$ μm correspond to $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = -2\pi$ or a monotonically decreasing function described by (8b). For each waveguide length, the selection between the three sub-functions is made by checking the sign of the 1st derivative of $\Delta\phi$ ($\partial\Delta\phi/\partial\lambda$) or, correspondingly, the sign of $\Delta(n_g L)$. Equation (8c) has to be applied when $\Delta(n_g L)$ equals 0 and changes sign for a wavelength shorter than λ_{dip} , while (8a) and (8b) have to be applied when $\Delta(n_g L)$ is negative or positive, respectively, in the spectral window below λ_{dip} . As can be easily

Fig. 3. Free spectral range calculated from (6) and (8) as a function of the length of the reference photonic waveguide in comparison with the values obtained from simulation.

recognized, this results to a FSR curve that increases with reference waveguide length as long as $L < 586$ μm to reach a maximum FSR value of 878 nm and then starts to decrease until L approaches 591.4 μm , i.e. as long as the sensor performs within the regime where dip splitting effect can take place. When L exceeds 591.4 μm , the FSR jumps rapidly to 337 nm and the sensor enters the regime where $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = -2\pi$ and, then, FSR starts again to decrease. The respective FSR values obtained from the circuit-level simulations seem to match perfectly with the blue-curve, validating (8) as an effective tool for calculating the correct FSR value. At the same time, the FSR values calculated by (6) can follow the simulated FSR only for values well below 100 nm, deviating significantly for reference waveguide lengths within 585-597 μm and failing to capture adequately the region where $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = 0$.

As a next step and in order to translate the above findings into an improved formula for sensitivity calculation, we solved (6) with respect to $\Delta(n_g L)$ and substitute this into (8), correlating in this way the real FSR value (obtained through 2nd order approximation of $\Delta\phi$) with the local FSR, as shown in the following equations:

$$FSR_{loc}|_{\mp 2\pi} = \frac{FSR^2 + \lambda FSR}{\mp FSR^2 \Delta\left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right) + \lambda_{dip}} \quad (9a)$$

$$FSR_{loc}|_0 = \frac{2(\lambda_{dip} - FSR)}{FSR \Delta\left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right)} \quad (9b)$$

Then, substituting (9) into (5), the sensitivity can be expressed as a function of the real FSR by the following equations, where $FSR > 0$.

$$S_{+2\pi} = \frac{L_{pl}}{\lambda_{dip}} \cdot \frac{FSR^2 + \lambda_{dip} FSR}{FSR^2 \Delta\left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right) + \lambda_{dip}} \quad (10a)$$

$$S_{-2\pi} = -\frac{L_{pl}}{\lambda_{dip}} \cdot \frac{FSR^2 + \lambda_{dip} FSR}{-FSR^2 \Delta\left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right) + \lambda_{dip}} \quad (10b)$$

$$S_0 = \frac{2L_{pl}}{\lambda_{dip}} \cdot \frac{\lambda_{dip} - FSR}{FSR \Delta\left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 n_{eff}}{\partial \lambda^2} L\right)} \quad (10c)$$

This set of equations provides a deeper insight and a new toolkit for effective design of the sensor circuit. It allows, first of all, the reliable calculation of sensitivity for a sensor device when the parameters of its real FSR, its waveguide effective index dispersion and its transducer length are known, with its validity extending both for small and large FSR layouts. On top of that, it reveals that sensitivity can improve even when sensor configurations have the same values for FSR, waveguide dispersion and transducer length by simply promoting its operational point to correspond to the $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = -2\pi$ operational region (tuning the reference photonic waveguide length), since (10b) provides the highest S among all three equations for the same set of parameters.

This can be easily visualized throughout the graphs

illustrated in Figs. 4 and 5. Fig. 4 depicts both FSR (left axis) and sensitivity (right axis) for varying reference photonic waveguide length obtained from (8) and (10), respectively, along with the respective simulated values (triangle markers). The plasmonic length was retained constant and equal to $70 \mu\text{m}$. Sensitivity is calculated with two different ways providing an additional means for verifying the new set of equations: firstly, for each waveguide length, the FSR obtained from (8) was used in (10) resulting in the solid, red curve, and secondly, the FSR of the corresponding simulated configuration was used resulting in the values depicted by the rectangle markers, considering again the same wavelength dip (1525 nm). It is obvious that in both cases, the sensitivity results obtained theoretically from (10) are well-matched with the respective simulated values exhibiting a maximum at the right edge of the dip splitting region. The reason for calculating the sensitivity with two ways is that although (8) results in significantly better accuracy in the prediction of the real FSR, there are still some small variations and the obtained results, in some cases, may not be exactly the same with those obtained from simulation (and considered as real), as it is also illustrated in Fig. 4 (blue curve and blue markers).

Moreover, Fig. 4 and (10) show that sensitivity depends not only on the sensor FSR but also on the relative lengths of the two arms and the dispersion characteristics of the waveguides that affect the form of $\Delta\phi$ function. This means that for a certain FSR, the sensitivity can have different values. To exemplify this, we selected three points from Fig. 4 ($L=586, 589$ and $592 \mu\text{m}$) that have the same FSR value (around 310 nm) but correspond to sensor configurations with different $\Delta\phi$ curves. For these cases, we plotted in Fig. 5 the spectral responses along with the sensitivity simulations and the corresponding $\Delta\phi$ curves. As can be seen in Fig. 5(a) and 5(d), $\Delta\phi$ is an increasing function for $L=586 \mu\text{m}$ and the sensor sensitivity at the dip of 1525 nm is equal to 10400 nm/RIU . In the case of $L=589 \mu\text{m}$, $\Delta\phi$ exhibits a local maximum resulting to $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = 0$ and to a sensitivity of 24000 nm/RIU for the same wavelength, as depicted in Fig. 5(b) and 5(e). Finally, $\Delta\phi$ is a decreasing function for $\lambda < 1525 \text{ nm}$ when $L=592 \mu\text{m}$, exhibiting a sensitivity of 90000 nm/RIU , as illustrated in Fig. 5(c) and 5(f).

Fig. 4. Free spectral range and sensitivity calculated from (8) and (10), respectively, as a function of the length of the reference photonic waveguide in comparison with the values obtained from simulation.

An additional consequence of the different $\Delta\phi$ behavior is that the wavelength shift changes direction depending on the monotonicity of $\Delta\phi$ around the wavelength dip, resulting in red shift for the cases of Figs. 5(a) and 5(b) and blue shift for the case of Fig. 5(c). With the above analysis, it becomes apparent that the newly reported design rule can be used (i) to predict correctly the FSR and sensitivity of the MZI and (ii) to increase the sensitivity of the sensor by up to a factor of 9 by simply tuning the length of reference arm within a range of only a few microns while maintaining the same FSR, plasmonic transducer length and waveguide geometries. Next section explains how sensitivity can be further improved by engineering the waveguide dispersion of plasmonic and photonic waveguides.

III. DISPERSION ENGINEERING FOR SENSITIVITY OPTIMIZATION

Following the mathematical analysis outlined in the previous section and the observations regarding sensitivity, this section describes how the above findings can be applied towards maximizing the sensitivity of a given plasmo-photonic sensor with a high FSR value near 300 nm by a) operating in the region where $\Delta\phi|_{FSR} = -2\pi$ [so (8b) and (10b) are utilized in what follows), and b) engineering the group index of either the photonic or the plasmonic waveguides. An initial investigation is performed in order to assess the effect of the waveguides width on sensitivity considering as the reference configuration the one described in [28], i.e. a sensor with $360 \text{ nm} \times 800 \text{ nm}$ photonic waveguides and a $100 \text{ nm} \times 7 \mu\text{m}$ plasmonic waveguide. After this initial investigation step and having validated our theoretical model through numerical circuit-level simulations, we proceeded with the full optimization of the plasmonic sensor utilizing the new equations (8) and (10).

A. Si_3N_4 waveguide dispersion engineering

This subsection considers a photonic waveguide of fixed thickness and a plasmonic waveguide with $7 \mu\text{m}$ width ($n_g=1.3866$) and 100 nm thickness, aiming to highlight how the sensor sensitivity can be further improved by manipulating the geometry of the photonic waveguide. Specifically, the Si_3N_4 waveguide illustrated in Fig. 1(b) has been numerically simulated in 2-dimensions in order to investigate its dispersion characteristics for different waveguide widths, always keeping the waveguide thickness constant and equal to 360 nm since this is in most cases defined by the targeted photonic platform. Fig. 6 depicts the effective and group index of the waveguide at 1525 nm for waveguide widths ranging from 600 to 1000 nm . As can be observed, both effective and group index increase with the waveguide width, with the group index exhibiting a steeper rise. Next, we calculated $\Delta(n_g L)$ and the sensitivity using (4) for sensor configurations with different Si_3N_4 widths, with their FSR remaining constant and equal to 300 nm by fine-tuning the length of the reference photonic waveguide within a range of two microns ($L_{600}-L_{1000} \approx 2 \mu\text{m}$). More specifically, for each photonic waveguide width, the appropriate lengths that lead to an FSR of 300 were defined by numerical circuit-level simulations and, then, were used for the calculation of $\Delta(n_g L)$ and sensitivity. As depicted in Fig. 7, $\Delta(n_g L)$ decreases with

Fig. 5. Spectral response, simulation sensitivity measurements and the respective $\Delta\phi$ curves for three different configurations having the same FSR but exhibiting different sensitivity: (a), (d) $L_{ref}=586 \mu\text{m}$, $\text{FSR}=311 \text{ nm}$, $S=10400 \text{ nm/RIU}$ (b), (e) $L_{ref}=589 \mu\text{m}$, $\text{FSR}=313 \text{ nm}$, $S=24000 \text{ nm/RIU}$ (c), (f) $L_{ref}=592 \mu\text{m}$, $\text{FSR}=313 \text{ nm}$, $S=90000 \text{ nm/RIU}$. Sensitivity measurements were performed for changes of the overlying liquid in the order of 10^{-4} towards having a distinguishable wavelength shift in all cases.

decreasing Si_3N_4 width, leading to an increasing sensitivity for decreasing waveguide width that reaches a maximum value of 183600 nm/RIU for a width of 600 nm . Conclusively, although the FSR is the same for all cases, sensitivity varies significantly between 50035 nm/RIU and 183600 nm/RIU for sensors with photonic waveguides of different width.

Fig. 6. Effective and group index of the SiN waveguide at 1525 nm as a function of SiN width.

As a next step, sensitivity measurements through frequency domain circuit-level simulations for each sensor configuration were performed in order to validate our theoretical model described by (8) and (10), and compare with the results predicted by the existing equation that correlates sensitivity with FSR, i.e. (5) when using the real FSR value. The simulations have been performed for refractive index change of the test liquid in the order of 10^{-5} and, as previously, for sensors with different Si_3N_4 waveguide widths but always configured to exhibit an FSR equal to 300 nm and a spectral dip at 1525 nm . The obtained sensitivity results are illustrated in Fig. 8 with respect to the photonic waveguide width (blue curve). Simulation results show that the sensitivity is maximum when employing SiN waveguides with 600 nm width achieving 128000 nm/RIU and decreases for wider waveguides till the value of 48000 nm/RIU for 1000 nm width. For the validation process, we considered the above simulated devices as the reference which means that we assumed a certain device with defined geometrical parameters (i.e waveguide widths and arm lengths) that lead to 300 nm FSR according to simulations. For these specific configurations, we calculated the theoretically expected sensitivity by means of (5) and (10). Firstly, (5) was used employing the real FSR of the simulated devices, i.e. 300 nm , resulting in the black curve of Fig. 8. As it can be seen,

Fig. 7. $\Delta(n_gL)$ and sensitivity from equation 4) versus SiN waveguide width for configurations with the same FSR=300 nm.

there is a considerable deviation of $(79.2 \pm 6.8)\%$ between these results and the respective values obtained from simulations (blue curve) showing clearly that (5) fails to predict the sensor sensitivity when its real FSR is known in such high-FSR and high-sensitivity configurations. It is also worth noting that (5) gives a constant value of sensitivity irrespective of the Si_3N_4 waveguide width since it is only affected by the sensor FSR, along with the plasmonic length and wavelength dip, which are also constant for all depicted configurations. Next, sensitivity was calculated by means of (10). Firstly, FSR of each previously simulated configuration was calculated through (8) and the obtained value was used in (10) for the calculation of sensitivity leading to the green curve. As can be observed, this curve follows the simulation results exhibiting a deviation only for 600 nm width and almost perfect match for wider waveguides verifying our analysis and showing that the maximum sensitivity is observed for SiN width of 600 nm. Afterwards, the real (simulated) FSR of the devices, i.e. 300 nm, was used in (10) leading to the red curve. It is obvious that this curve exhibits almost perfect match with the respective simulation results with only a small deviation of $(3.4 \pm 1.8)\%$ validating (10) as an effective tool for calculating the sensor sensitivity when its real FSR is known in contrast to (5) that has been proved inappropriate for the accurate prediction of the sensor sensitivity. Specifically, the significantly larger deviation between (10) and (5) when using the real FSR stems from the equivalent deviation between the approximated, local FSR given by (6) and the improved approximation of (8) that results in values almost equal to the real FSR. In particular, the FSR values obtained from (8) are very close to the simulated values with a small deviation of $(0.9 \pm 0.8)\%$. On the contrary, the values given by (6) exhibit an average error of 555% with a standard deviation of 351%. For instance, when the width of the Si_3N_4 waveguide is 800 nm, the sensor FSR is 302.5 nm according to simulation while the expected values from (6) and (8) are 1541 nm and 303.4 nm, respectively.

Finally, Fig. 9 depicts the sensitivity obtained from (10b) as a function of the sensor FSR at 1525 nm for different Si_3N_4

Fig. 8. Sensor sensitivity as a function of SiN width. In each case the FSR was kept constant and equal to 300 nm.

waveguide widths (solid curves) in comparison to the equivalent results when dispersion is neglected (dashed curve) [28] and the respective simulated values (markers) for sensors with FSR=50, 100, 150, 200, 250 and 300 nm. As it can be seen, there is perfect match between simulated values and the results obtained from (10) in contrast to the case of zero dispersion, showcasing the increased accuracy offered by the new equation (10) in predicting the sensor sensitivity when its real FSR is known. Additionally, it is shown clearly that when 2nd order dispersion is taken into account and the FSR is larger than 100 nm, the sensitivity is not univocally defined by FSR but the dispersion characteristics of the waveguides play also a significant role.

B. Plasmonic waveguide dispersion engineering

This section provides a similar analysis on how the sensor sensitivity can be optimized when engineering the dispersion

Fig. 9. Sensitivity as a function of real FSR. Solid curves: results obtained from (10) where 2nd order dispersion is included. Dashed curve: obtained from the equation.

properties of its plasmonic waveguide segment while keeping the photonic waveguide characteristics constant. This is achieved by varying the width of the plasmonic stripe waveguide considering an 800 nm wide Si_3N_4 waveguide ($n_g=1.8883$). Fig. 10 depicts the plasmonic waveguide group index at 1525 nm for different widths of the Au stripe ranging from 6 to 9 μm . The effective index increases slightly with the stripe width while the group index shows a more pronounced variation with a maximum at 6.5 μm . Fig. 11 shows $\Delta(n_g L)$ and the sensitivity calculated from (4) with respect to the plasmonic stripe width for configurations with the FSR equal to 300 nm at 1525 nm. In order to retain the FSR constant, the length of the reference photonic waveguide was fine-tuned within a maximum range of 150 nanometers ($L_{6\mu\text{m}}-L_{9\mu\text{m}}\approx 150$ nm) by means of circuit-level simulations for each configuration employing a plasmonic waveguide of different width. As can be easily seen, the sensitivity according to (4) exhibits a maximum of 90500 nm/RIU for 6.5 μm width that corresponds to the minimum $\Delta(n_g L)$.

Next, sensitivity of the above configurations was calculated by means of the two equations that correlate the sensor sensitivity with the FSR, i.e. the existing equation (5) and the new equation (10). As mentioned in the previous section, we assumed a certain device with defined geometrical parameters (i.e. waveguide widths and lengths) that lead to 300 nm FSR according to simulations. In order to highlight the increased accuracy of (10), the obtained results are depicted in Fig. 12 in comparison with results obtained from circuit-level simulations of the equivalent sensors for $\Delta n_{\text{liquid}}=10^{-5}$. Specifically, Fig. 12 illustrates the sensor sensitivity as a function of the plasmonic waveguide width. The first curve (blue) corresponds to the simulation results and shows that a maximum sensitivity of 71000 nm/RIU is achieved for W_{Au} equal to 7 μm . The second curve (black) depicts the sensitivity of each sensor configuration predicted by (5) when using the real FSR of the device, i.e. 300 nm. It is obvious that (5) leads to a constant value irrespective of the plasmonic waveguide width that exhibits a considerable deviation in the range of $(72\pm 10)\%$ compared to the simulation results showing once more its ineffectiveness in predicting the sensor sensitivity when its real

Fig. 10. Effective and group index of plasmonic waveguide at 1525 nm as a function of Au width.

Fig. 11. $\Delta(n_g L)$ and sensitivity versus plasmonic waveguide width, same FSR=300 nm.

FSR is known. The next curve (green) shows the theoretically calculated sensitivity from (10) when using the FSR of the sensor calculated through (8). As can be observed, this curve follows the simulation results exhibiting almost perfect match for plasmonic waveguides of 7 μm and wider. A considerable deviation is only observed for 6.5 μm which leads to a shifted maximum at 6.5 μm instead of 7 μm according to simulation. Finally, the last curve illustrates the sensitivity obtained through (10) using the real FSR of each sensor which is equal to 300 nm for all configurations. As it can be seen, for Au stripe widths equal to or greater than 7 μm , (10) provides good agreement with the respective simulation results with a deviation of $(12.5\pm 7.5)\%$ capturing also the same maximum with simulation. For Au widths less than 7 μm , larger deviations are observed that reach 34% and 38% for a width of 6 μm and 6.5 μm , respectively. This mainly owes to the analogous larger deviation in the calculation of FSR through (8). Specifically, when $W_{\text{Au}}\geq 7$ μm there is a very good agreement between the FSR given by (8) and simulation with an average error of

Fig. 12. Sensor sensitivity as a function of Au width. In each case the FSR was kept constant and equal to 300 nm.

(2.5 ± 2)%, while for widths of 6 μm and 6.5 μm , the respective deviations are 43.4% and 16.5%. The origin of this increased FSR deviation at these shorter plasmonic stripes lies in the different distribution of the plasmonic field: the plasmonic mode starts escape from the stripe horizontal surface and to concentrate also at the metallic edges and the vertical metal sides, which most probably leads to a higher order form of effective index versus wavelength. As a result, the 2nd order approximation of $\Delta\phi$ function is less accurate resulting in the above deviations. However, the above discrepancies in sensitivity are still significantly smaller than the respective ones provided by (5) when using the real FSR value in its expression suggesting the importance of our theoretical model in predicting the FSR and sensitivity of a certain MZI sensor configuration through (8) and (10), respectively.

C. Sensitivity optimization

Having validated the effectiveness of the new equations (8) and (10), we proceed with the optimization of a plasmo-photonic MZI sensor with a certain FSR value utilizing only these equations. In particular, for each combination of photonic and plasmonic waveguide widths, firstly, we calculated the required reference photonic waveguide length for attaining 300 nm FSR through (8b). Next, for this FSR and L_{ref} , we calculated the expected sensitivity by means of (10b). The obtained results are depicted in the contour plot of Fig. 13 showing that the maximum sensitivity is achieved for $W_{\text{SiN}}=600$ nm and $W_{\text{Au}}=7$ μm , reaching the ultra-high value of 128000 nm/RIU. It is of great importance to highlight that the above optimization process requires only 2D simulations of the waveguides in order to extract the dispersion properties of the waveguides and the execution of a simple script that solves the two presented equations. In the absence of these equations, thirty-five circuit-level simulations should be performed in order to obtain the same graph which, without doubt, would be much more time consuming.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we demonstrated for the first time a concrete theoretical framework that can accurately calculate the FSR of

Fig. 13. Sensor sensitivity for different photonic and plasmonic waveguide widths for sensor configurations with 300 nm FSR.

Mach-Zehnder interferometric refractive index sensors as well as their sensitivity when their real FSR value is known. As opposed to the state-of-the-art mathematical relationship between sensitivity and FSR, our theory takes into account both the dispersion and the dip splitting effect, allowing for reliable FSR and sensitivity predictions in even high-FSR configurations (that typically offer higher sensitivities) for which conventional 1st order approximation methods fail. We validated our theory through numerical, circuit-level simulations implemented for plasmo-photonic MZI sensors with high FSR values of hundreds of nanometers, confirming the theoretical results and showing that sensitivity can be boosted to $>10^5$ nm/RIU by simply optimizing the width of the photonic or the plasmonic waveguides exploiting the dispersion effect offering, in this way, greater than 10 times improvement of sensitivity for configurations with the same FSR. Hence, our analytical formula unravels a new set of possibilities for sensitivity optimization prior the sensor fabrication phase.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. F. Gavela, D. G. García, J. C. Ramirez, and L. M. Lechuga, "Last advances in silicon-based optical biosensors," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 1–15, 2016, doi: 10.3390/s16030285.
- [2] M. C. Estevez, M. Alvarez, and L. M. Lechuga, "Integrated optical devices for lab-on-a-chip biosensing applications," *Laser Photonics Rev.*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 463–487, 2012, doi: 10.1002/lpor.201100025.
- [3] S. TalebiFard *et al.*, "Optimized sensitivity of Silicon-on-Insulator (SOI) strip waveguide resonator sensor," *Biomed. Opt. Express*, vol. 8, no. 2, p. 500, 2017, doi: 10.1364/boe.8.000500.
- [4] X. Ma, K. Chen, J. Wu, and L. Wang, "Low-Cost and Highly Sensitive Liquid Refractive Index Sensor Based on Polymer Horizontal Slot Waveguide," *Photonic Sensors*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 7–15, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s13320-019-0560-y.
- [5] C. A. Barrios, "Optical slot-waveguide based biochemical sensors," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 4751–4765, 2009, doi: 10.3390/s90604751.
- [6] J. Flueckiger *et al.*, "Sub-wavelength grating for enhanced ring resonator biosensor," *Opt. Express*, vol. 24, no. 14, p. 15672, 2016, doi: 10.1364/oe.24.015672.
- [7] R. Caroselli *et al.*, "Experimental study of the sensitivity of a porous silicon ring resonator sensor using continuous in-flow measurements," *Opt. Express*, vol. 25, no. 25, p. 31651, 2017, doi: 10.1364/oe.25.031651.
- [8] A. Manolis *et al.*, "Bringing Plasmonics into CMOS Photonic Foundries: Aluminum Plasmonics on Si₃N₄ for Biosensing Applications," *J. Light. Technol.*, vol. 37, no. 21, pp. 5516–5524, 2019, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2019.2937454.
- [9] T. Claes, J. G. Molera, K. De Vos, E. Schacht, R. Baets, and P. Bienstman, "Label-free biosensing with a slot-waveguide-based ring resonator in silicon on insulator," *IEEE Photonics J.*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 197–204, 2009, doi: 10.1109/JPHOT.2009.2031596.
- [10] X. Sun, D. Dai, L. Thylén, and L. Wosinski, "Double-slot hybrid plasmonic ring resonator used for optical sensors and modulators," *Photonics*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 1116–1130, 2015, doi: 10.3390/photonics2041116.
- [11] Y. Zhang, S. Han, S. Zhang, P. Liu, and Y. Shi, "High-Q and High-Sensitivity Photonic Crystal Cavity Sensor," *IEEE Photonics J.*, vol. 7, no. 5, 2015, doi: 10.1109/JPHOT.2015.2469131.
- [12] A. Di Falco, L. O'Faolain, and T. F. Krauss, "Chemical sensing in slotted photonic crystal heterostructure cavities," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 94, no. 6, pp. 96–99, 2009, doi: 10.1063/1.3079671.
- [13] D. Duval, J. Osmond, S. Dante, C. Domínguez, and L. M. Lechuga, "Grating couplers integrated on Mach-Zehnder interferometric biosensors operating in the visible range," *IEEE Photonics J.*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2013, doi: 10.1109/JPHOT.2013.2251873.
- [14] Q. Liu *et al.*, "Highly sensitive Mach-Zehnder interferometer biosensor based on silicon nitride slot waveguide," *Sensors Actuators, B Chem.*, vol. 188, pp. 681–688, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.snb.2013.07.053.
- [15] B. Sepveda *et al.*, "Optical biosensor microsystems based on the integration of highly sensitive Mach-Zehnder interferometer devices," *J.*

- Opt. A Pure Appl. Opt.*, vol. 8, no. 7, 2006, doi: 10.1088/1464-4258/8/7/S41.
- [16] A. Brandenburg, R. Krauter, C. Künzel, M. Stefan, and H. Schulte, "Interferometric sensor for detection of surface-bound bioreactions," *Appl. Opt.*, vol. 39, no. 34, p. 6396, 2000, doi: 10.1364/ao.39.006396.
- [17] K. Schmitt, B. Schirmer, C. Hoffmann, A. Brandenburg, and P. Meyrueis, "Interferometric biosensor based on planar optical waveguide sensor chips for label-free detection of surface bound bioreactions," *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, vol. 22, no. 11, pp. 2591–2597, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.bios.2006.10.016.
- [18] T. Claes, W. Bogaerts, and P. Bienstman, "Experimental characterization of a silicon photonic biosensor consisting of two cascaded ring resonators based on the Vernier-effect and introduction of a curve fitting method for an improved detection limit," *Opt. Express*, vol. 18, no. 22, p. 22747, 2010, doi: 10.1364/oe.18.022747.
- [19] X. Jiang, J. Ye, J. Zou, M. Li, and J.-J. He, "Cascaded silicon-on-insulator double-ring sensors operating in high-sensitivity transverse-magnetic mode," *Opt. Lett.*, vol. 38, no. 8, p. 1349, 2013, doi: 10.1364/ol.38.001349.
- [20] Y. Liu, Y. Li, M. Li, and J.-J. He, "High-sensitivity and wide-range optical sensor based on three cascaded ring resonators," *Opt. Express*, vol. 25, no. 2, p. 972, 2017, doi: 10.1364/oe.25.000972.
- [21] F. J. Blanco *et al.*, "Microfluidic-optical integrated CMOS compatible devices for label-free biochemical sensing," *J. Micromechanics Microengineering*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1006–1016, 2006, doi: 10.1088/0960-1317/16/5/018.
- [22] X. Jiang, Y. Chen, F. Yu, L. Tang, M. Li, and J.-J. He, "High-sensitivity optical biosensor based on cascaded Mach-Zehnder interferometer and ring resonator using Vernier effect," *Opt. Lett.*, vol. 39, no. 22, p. 6363, 2014, doi: 10.1364/ol.39.006363.
- [23] K. Misiakos *et al.*, "Broad-band Mach-Zehnder interferometers as high performance refractive index sensors: Theory and monolithic implementation," *Opt. Express*, vol. 22, no. 8, p. 8856, 2014, doi: 10.1364/oe.22.008856.
- [24] A. Manolis *et al.*, "Plasmonics co-integrated with silicon nitride photonics for high-sensitivity interferometric biosensing," *Opt. Express*, vol. 27, no. 12, p. 17102, 2019, doi: 10.1364/oe.27.017102.
- [25] X. Sun, D. Dai, L. Thylén, and L. Wosinski, "High-sensitivity liquid refractive-index sensor based on a Mach-Zehnder interferometer with a double-slot hybrid plasmonic waveguide," *Opt. Express*, vol. 23, no. 20, p. 25688, 2015, doi: 10.1364/oe.23.025688.
- [26] X. Sun, L. Thylén, and L. Wosinski, "Hollow hybrid plasmonic Mach-Zehnder sensor," *Opt. Lett.*, vol. 42, no. 4, p. 807, 2017, doi: 10.1364/ol.42.000807.
- [27] A. Manolis *et al.*, "Ultra-sensitive refractive index sensor using CMOS plasmonic transducers on silicon photonic interferometric platform," *Opt. Express*, vol. 28, no. 14, pp. 20992–21001, 2020, doi: 10.1364/oe.383435.
- [28] E. Chatzianagnostou *et al.*, "Scaling the Sensitivity of Integrated Plasmonic-Photonic Interferometric Sensors," *ACS Photonics*, vol. 6, no. 7, pp. 1664–1673, 2019, doi: 10.1021/acsp Photonics.8b01683.
- [29] Y. Xie, M. Zhang, and D. Dai, "Design rule of Mach-Zehnder interferometer sensors for ultra-high sensitivity," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 20, no. 9, pp. 1–7, 2020, doi: 10.3390/s20092640.
- [30] M. Kitsara, K. Misiakos, I. Raptis, and E. Makarona, "Integrated optical frequency-resolved Mach-Zehnder interferometers for label-free affinity sensing," *Opt. Express*, vol. 18, no. 8, p. 8193, 2010, doi: 10.1364/oe.18.008193.
- [31] R. Levy, S. Ruschin, and D. Goldring, "Critical sensitivity effect in a waveguided interferometer sensor," *Opt. InfoBase Conf. Pap.*, vol. 34, no. 19, pp. 3023–3025, 2009, doi: 10.1364/fio.2009.fmj8.
- [32] R. Levy and S. Ruschin, "Critical sensitivity in hetero-modal interferometric sensor using spectral interrogation," *Opt. Express*, vol. 16, no. 25, p. 20516, 2008, doi: 10.1364/oe.16.020516.
- [33] Y. Zhang, J. Zou, and J.-J. He, "Temperature sensor with enhanced sensitivity based on silicon Mach-Zehnder interferometer with waveguide group index engineering," *Opt. Express*, vol. 26, no. 20, p. 26057, 2018, doi: 10.1364/oe.26.026057.
- [34] H. Luo, Q. Sun, Z. Xu, W. Jia, D. Liu, and L. Zhang, "Microfiber-based inline Mach-Zehnder interferometer for dual-parameter measurement," *IEEE Photonics J.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1–8, 2015, doi: 10.1109/JPHOT.2015.2395133.
- [35] H. Luo *et al.*, "Refractive index sensitivity characteristics near the dispersion turning point of the multimode microfiber-based Mach-Zehnder interferometer," *Opt. Lett.*, vol. 40, no. 21, p. 5042, 2015, doi: 10.1364/ol.40.005042.
- [36] J. Li *et al.*, "Ultrasensitive refractive-index sensors based on rectangular silica microfibers," *Opt. Lett.*, vol. 36, no. 18, p. 3593, 2011, doi: 10.1364/ol.36.003593.
- [37] Lukas Chrostowski, *Silicon Photonics Design: From Device to System*. 2010.
- [38] W. Bogaerts *et al.*, "Silicon microring resonators," *Laser Photonics Rev.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 47–73, 2012, doi: 10.1002/lpor.201100017.
- [39] G. Dabos *et al.*, "Plasmonic Stripes in Aqueous Environment Co-Integrated with Si₃N₄ Photonics," *IEEE Photonics J.*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2018, doi: 10.1109/JPHOT.2018.2792533.
- [40] "Lumerical Solutions, Inc., <http://www.lumerical.com/tcad-products/interconnect/>."
- [41] "Lumerical Solutions, Inc., <http://www.lumerical.com/tcad-products/mode/>."